

Gravimetric Determination of Nickel(II) and Palladium(II) and Their Separation from Binary Mixture with 3-(*p*-Acetophenyl)-1-Methyltriazene-N-oxide

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3-(*p*-Acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide has been used successfully for gravimetric determination of Nickel(II) (3-30 mg) and Palladium(II) (2.5-40 mg) with an accuracy of $\pm 0.14\%$ and $\pm 0.16\%$ respectively. The precipitation of Ni and Pd complexes start at pH 5.0 and 0.5 and are quantitative within the pH range 6.5-10.2 and 1.0-8.0 respectively. The greenish yellow coloured Ni-complex and buff coloured Pd-complexes correspond with the formula $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3)_2$ respectively and can be weighed as such after drying at 120° . The reagent has also been used in the separation and determination of one in its binary mixture with the other. Determinations in presence of different foreign ions have also been reported.

DIMETHYL glyoxime¹ is the most widely applied and accepted gravimetric reagent for both Ni(II) and Pd(II). Objections to the precipitation of Pd(II) with DMG are the voluminous character of the precipitate and interference due to Platinum and Nickel. The other reagents comprising of various thioligands²⁻⁴, triazenes⁵⁻⁷ have also been reported for the determination of either the Ni(II) or Pd(II) or both, but most of them involve narrow pH-range and/or consume much time. In this paper we recommend the reagent, 3-(*p*-acetophenyl) 1-methyltriazene-N-oxide⁸ which reacts with Nickel(II) and Palladium(II) quantitatively in the pH range 6.5-10.2 and 1.0-8.0 forming thermally stable greenish yellow $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and buff coloured $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3)_2$ complexes respectively. The estimation procedures recommended for both the metal ions Ni(II) and Pd(II) are very simple, cover wide pH-range and consume much less time. The compact nature of the precipitates render them easily washable with redistilled water only. As there lies a clear margin in the pH ranges for the estimation of the two metal ions they can be separated from their binary mixtures simply by controlling the pH. The interferences due to almost all ions have been removed by controlling pH or using suitable masking agents.

Experimental

3-(p-Acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide: The reagent was prepared by the method as reported⁸.

Nickel(II) solution: Nickel chloride (E. Merck) was dissolved in very dilute hydrochloric acid and the metal content was determined gravimetrically with dimethylglyoxime¹.

Palladium(II) solution: Palladium chloride (E. Merck) was dissolved in strong hydrochloric acid and palladium was estimated also with dimethylglyoxime¹.

Diverse ions: Solutions of other ions were prepared from the chloride or nitrate salts of cations and from the sodium, potassium and ammonium salts of anions. A few drops of suitable acid was added to prevent hydrolysis where necessary. All the chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Apparatus: All the pH measurements were carried out with a cambridge bench model pH-meter.

Determination of Nickel(II): To an aliquot of standard solution of nickel (3.0-30.0 mg) present in 200 ml at pH 3.0-4.0 heated on a boiling water bath, solution of the reagent (30.0-250.0 mg) in ethanol was added with stirring. The pH then raised gradually with ammonia solution to 6.5-10.2. The greenish yellow precipitate was digested for half an hour. The complex was then filtered through weighed gooch crucible (No. 4) and washed with hot (80°) water and dried at 120° and weighed as $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to constant weight. The conversion factor is 0.1226. Results of one of several determinations are furnished in Table I.

Determination of Palladium(II): The procedure is almost the same as that of nickel. To the palladium solution (2.5-40 mg) present in 200 ml heated on a boiling water bath, the reagent (20.0-240.0 mg) dissolved in minimum volume of alcohol was added gradually with stirring. The pH was

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF NICKEL AND PALLADIUM

Metal ion taken	Weight (mg)	Wt of the complex (mg)	Metal ion found (mg)	Relative error (%)
Ni ²⁺	3.0	24.5, 24.4	3.00, 2.99	nil, -0.33
	12.0	97.8, 98.0	11.99, 12.01	-0.08, +0.08
	21.0	171.3, 171.0	21.00, 20.96	nil, -0.19
	30.0	244.7, 245.0	30.00, 30.03	nil, +0.10
Pd ²⁺	2.48	11.41, 11.45	2.47, 2.48	-0.40, nil
	9.92	45.71, 45.66	9.91, 9.90	-0.10, -0.20
	19.84	91.60, 91.42	19.86, 19.82	+0.10, -0.10
	39.68	183.08, 183.30	39.69, 39.74	+0.02, +0.15

then adjusted between 1.0 and 8.0 with ammonia solution. The buff coloured precipitate was kept over the boiling waterbath for digestion till the precipitate quagulated which required 20 minutes. The precipitate then filtered through weighed gooch crucible (No. 3) and washed several times with hot water, dried at 120° and finally weighed as Pd(C₉H₁₀O₂N₃)₂. The gravimetric factor is 0.2168. The results of these determinations are given in Table 1.

Separation and Determination of Ni(II) and Pd(II) Present in a Binary mixture : The pH of the binary mixture containing Ni(II) and Pd(II) in solution was adjusted at 2.0 and heated on boiling water bath. Slight excess amount of reagent than what is required for the estimation of the total metal ions, dissolved in alcohol was gradually added with stirring. The precipitate of Pd-complex formed almost instantaneously quagulated on digestion for 20 minutes. It was filtered, washed and the metal content determined as described earlier. The volume of the filtrate containing nickel and the washings was then reduced to 200 ml and the metal content was determined following the procedure described. The results follow in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SEPARATION AND DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM AND NICKEL FROM BINARY MIXTURES

Metal taken (mg)		Metal found (mg)		Relative error%	
Ni	Pd	Ni	Pd	Ni	Pd
4.50	4.96	4.49	4.97	-0.22	+0.20
4.50	14.88	4.48	14.87	-0.44	-0.07
13.50	4.96	13.48	4.96	-0.15	nil
21.00	21.08	21.05	21.05	+0.23	-0.14

Procedure in Presence of Diverse Ions : When the estimations are to be done in presence of foreign ions, tartrate is added prior to the addition of the reagent and the pH-values for Palladium and Nickel estimations are kept at 2.0 and 7.0 respectively. Results of one of the several determinations are recorded in Table 3. Suitable masking agents used in the determinations of Ni and Pd are tartrate in general, phosphoric acid (a), ascorbic acid (b), ammonium acetate (c) and potassium iodide (d) preferably when required. Chromium(III), Manganese(II), Copper(II) and Cobalt(II) do not interfere with the determination of palladium but

do with nickel estimation. Disodium EDTA, anions as cyanide and large excess of citrate, oxalate and phosphate also interfere, 100 mg of oxalate, citrate, 200 mg of phosphate are however tolerable in both the cases. Even trace amount of Au(III) interferes with Pd(II) estimation. For determination of either metal ions in presence of Ag(I) and Pb(II) nitric acid was used in place of hydrochloric acid.

TABLE 3—SEPARATION OF NICKEL(II) OR PALLADIUM(II) FROM DIVERSE IONS

Diverse ions (mg)	Ni taken : 9.0 mg		Pd taken : 9.92 mg	
	Ni found (mg)	Relative error%	Pd found (mg)	Relative error%
Tartrate (100)	9.01	+0.11	9.92	nil
Fluoride (500)	9.00	nil	9.90	-0.20
Thiocyanate (100)	8.98	-0.22		interferes
Arsenate (100)	9.00	nil	9.91	-0.10
Borate (100)	8.99	-0.11	9.89	-0.30
Fe ²⁺ (30)	8.97 a,b	-0.33	9.94(a),b	+0.20
Al ³⁺ (30)	9.02	+0.22	9.90	-0.20
Bi ³⁺ (30)	9.00	nil	9.91	-0.10
As ³⁺ (30)	8.99	-0.11	9.89	-0.30
Be ²⁺ (50)	9.02	+0.22	9.92	nil
Ni ²⁺ (50)			9.90	-0.20
Zn ²⁺ (50)	9.00	nil	9.88	-0.40
Hg ²⁺ (50)	8.99 (d)	-0.11	9.89	-0.30
Cd ²⁺ (50)	9.02 (d)	+0.22	9.92	nil
Pb ²⁺ (30)	9.03	+0.33	9.95	+0.30
Ag ¹⁺ (30)	9.01	+0.11	9.93	+0.10
Mg ²⁺ (50)	9.00	nil	9.92	nil
Sn ²⁺ (30)	9.02	+0.22	9.88	-0.40
MoO ₄ ²⁻ (50)	8.99	-0.11	9.90	-0.20
WO ₄ ²⁻ (50)	9.00	nil	9.91	-0.10
UO ₃ ²⁺ (50)	8.99 ^c	-0.11	9.88	-0.40
ZrO ²⁺ (50)	9.02	+0.22	9.92	nil
HfO ²⁺ (50)	8.98	-0.22	9.93	+0.10
VO ₃ ⁺ (50)	9.01	+0.11	9.91	-0.10
Nb ⁵⁺ (50)	8.99	-0.11	9.89	-0.30
Ta ⁵⁺ (50)	9.02	+0.22	9.92	nil
Rh ³⁺ (50)	8.97	-0.33	9.88	-0.40
Pt ⁴⁺ (50)	9.00	nil	9.92	nil
Os ⁴⁺ (50)	9.03	+0.33	9.91	-0.10
TiO ²⁺ (50)	9.01	+0.11	9.89	-0.30

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH and Reagent Concentration : With fixed amount of metal content (Ni=9.0 mg, Pd=9.92 mg) both nickel and palladium were estimated as described at varying pH values. It was found that the precipitation of nickel and palladium complexes start at pH 5.0 and 0.5 and are quantitative within the pH-range 6.5-10.2 and 1.0-8.0 respectively. At fixed pH values (7.0 for nickel and 2.0 for palladium) definite amount of the metal contents were estimated with varying quantities of the reagent. Amount of reagents required for complete precipitation of both the metal ions from its solution was 1.2 times of the theoretical amount of the reagent. Determinations in presence of foreign ions require slight more (2-2.5 times) reagent.

Properties and Composition of the Complexes : Both the nickel and palladium-3-(p-acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-oxide complexes are practically insoluble in water and 30% (v/v) ethanol. The

nickel complex is appreciably soluble in absolute alcohol, acetone, benzene and chloroform, however, the palladium complex is much less soluble in those solvents. Both the complexes are almost insoluble in carbon tetrachloride and ether. The recrystallised greenish-yellow nickel and buff-coloured palladium complexes melt with decomposition at 236° and 265° respectively. Both the complexes were analysed for nitrogen by Duma's method and metal content after decomposing with acid by the usual procedure with DMG. The results obtained were in fair agreement with the theoretical results corresponding to molecular formula

[Ni calc : 12.26% N calc : 17.53%]
[Ni Found : 12.16% N found : 17.80%]

[Pd calc : 21.68% N calc : 17.11%]
[Pd found : 21.61% N found : 16.92%]

As the triazene complexes are usually explosive in nature weight loss due to water molecule of the nickel complex could not be tried thermogravimetrically. I.R. spectral bands at 3175 cm^{-1} and 988 cm^{-1} in the free ligand due to N-H and N-O stretches disappears and shifts to lower frequencies respectively in the Ni(II) and Pd(II) chelates. This indicates that chelation takes place through N-H by proton displacement and through 'O' of N-O with the formation of M-O bond. Moreover appearance of a new band at 3150 cm^{-1} in Ni(II) chelate shows the presence of water molecules in the compound. The nickel chelate has been found to be diamagnetic suggesting square planer configuration and hence water molecules present are probably

lattice water. Pd(II) complex is as usual diamagnetic and appears to possess square planer stereochemistry.

Precision and Accuracy : The average error for twenty-five determinations for each of the metal ion nickel(II) and palladium(II) are $\pm 0.14\%$ and $\pm 0.16\%$ respectively.

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